

An Artificial Intelligence Approach to Manage Vehicles Motorway Entries in Congested Traffic

Antonio Salcuni
Politecnico di Bari
Bari, Italy
antonio.salcuni@poliba.it

Gaetano Volpe
Politecnico di Bari
Bari, Italy
gaetano.volpe@poliba.it

Agostino Marcello Mangini
Politecnico di Bari
Bari, Italy
agostinomarcello.mangini@poliba.it

Maria Pia Fanti
Politecnico di Bari
Bari, Italy
mariapia.fanti@poliba.it

Abstract—Efficient traffic management in high-density urban areas is a critical challenge, specifically in highway entry ramps and merging points. This paper deals with the problem of managing vehicles that have to enter highway ramps and intersections. The problem is formulated as an optimization task to minimize sudden braking, waiting times, and collision risks. A Deep Reinforcement Learning approach based on the Actor-Critic framework is proposed to train the intelligent traffic light agent managing the vehicle entries. The reward function is designed to dynamically balance safety and efficiency by reducing braking events and congestion. A simulation campaign is performed in a high-density merging scenario located in central-northern Italy at the intersection between the A1 Highway and the A14 Motorway. The results demonstrate the benefits obtained in reduced traffic flow and increased safety.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid increase in vehicular traffic in urban and peri-urban areas has made the management of highway entries and critical intersections increasingly complex. Consequently, traditional rule-based and model-based optimization methods struggle to adapt to highly dynamic and uncertain environments. In response to these challenges, Artificial Intelligence (AI) based techniques, such as Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL), have shown promising results in adaptive traffic management. [1]

Incident-induced congestion, a major issue in highway traffic management, accounts for over 60 percent of delays on major roads, leading to significant economic and environmental costs [2]. Traditional approaches, such as model-based optimization methods, often fail to adapt to highly dynamic traffic scenarios. Recent advances in DRL-based techniques have shown great promise in addressing these challenges by enabling agents to learn adaptive traffic management strategies.

Indeed, DRL has emerged as a powerful framework for addressing dynamic decision-making in uncertain and complex settings [3]. These approaches have proven effective in domains such as service robots, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), and dynamic routing problems. For example, recent

This study is part of the MOST - Sustainable Mobility National Research Center, receiving funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (PIANO NAZIONALE DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA (PNRR) MISSIONE 4 COMPONENTE 2, INVESTIMENTO 1.4 D.D. 1033 17/06/2022, CN0000 0023) and part of the IN2CCAM project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101076791.

studies have applied DRL to solve the Dynamic Traveling Salesman Problem, demonstrating its potential in complex combinatorial environments [4].

Traditional navigation methods often struggle with uncertainties, whereas DRL enables systems to learn navigation policies through trial and error, leveraging sensor data and kinematic information to handle challenging scenarios. In vehicular networks, multi-agent DRL systems have been employed to coordinate tasks such as dynamic resource migration and edge service offloading [5].

In addition to DRL, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) has also been explored as a complementary method, especially for traffic signal optimization. PSO dynamically adjusts traffic light timings to suit real-time conditions, outperforming traditional fixed-timing controllers and other evolutionary algorithms, such as Genetic Algorithms (GA) and Ant Colony Optimization [6]. Recent research on PSO-based control using UAV swarms further highlights the effectiveness of swarm intelligence in large-scale optimization scenarios [7].

Simulation platforms such as Simulation of Urban Mobility (SUMO) play a crucial role in testing and validating these solutions. Specifically, SUMO provides realistic traffic environments that support the development of AI-based traffic management frameworks by generating high-fidelity traffic scenarios [8].

Efficient traffic management in high-density urban areas is a critical challenge, specifically in highway entry ramps and merging points, where vehicles must integrate smoothly into high-speed traffic flows. The problem of merging optimization involves balancing traffic throughput, minimizing sudden braking events, and reducing the risk of collisions. Traditional traffic control systems struggle to adapt to real-time conditions, necessitating advanced learning-based solutions.

This paper addresses the highway merging problem by proposing an intelligent traffic light that manages the input of vehicles in the highway based on the traffic flow level. In the proposed method, the traffic light is an agent that is trained by a DRL approach based on the Actor-Critic framework [9]. The use of Actor-Critic methods has been shown to offer stable and sample-efficient training in continuous decision spaces, making it suitable for complex traffic environments [10].

The proposed intelligent traffic light is implemented by a simulation analysis on a case study involving a high-density intersection of northern Italy between the A1 highway and

the A14 motorway. The study focuses on optimizing vehicle entry at critical congestion points, particularly at highway on-ramps, where sudden braking and inefficient merging strategies significantly impact traffic flow and safety.

The results demonstrate significant improvements in traffic flow, safety metrics, and efficiency. This study contributes by addressing the interplay between vehicles and infrastructure, integrating DRL and advanced simulation tools, and bridging the gap between theoretical advancements and practical applications.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the problem formulation and the basic definitions of the DRL approach. Section III describes the DRL strategy applied to the considered problem and Section IV presents and discusses the case study. Finally, Section V reports conclusions and future works.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Traffic control mechanisms can integrate predefined routes with intelligent signals to regulate merging operations. Traffic routes define different vehicle interactions within the merging zone: vehicles entering the main traffic stream (\mathcal{R}_{in}), those changing direction and requiring lane transitions (\mathcal{R}_{turn}), and those traveling without lane changes (\mathcal{R}_{main}), which serves as a reference for evaluating interactions between merging and non-merging vehicles. Intelligent traffic signals operate through multiple phases to ensure smooth merging. The \mathcal{G} (Green) phase allows movement, while \mathcal{R} (Red) forces vehicles to stop. Intermediate phases such as \mathcal{GR} and \mathcal{RG} regulate merging by allowing traffic from one route while restricting the other. The system coordinates vehicle entries and merging maneuvers: S_{merge} manages merging from a secondary road, alternating between \mathcal{GR} and \mathcal{RG} to prevent conflicts. S_{entry} controls vehicle entry at a regulated access point, alternating between \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{R} without stopping the main flow. Fig. 1 illustrates the environment: first, the merging route through which vehicles enter the second route; second, the route that allows access to the highway. Both routes are regulated by traffic lights:

Fig. 1. The figure illustrates two different merging strategies in a highway scenario: S_{merge} (left) and S_{entry} (right). The right-side image represents the natural continuation of the flow depicted on the left. Vehicles, after merging from two on-ramps regulated by the traffic light S_{merge} , continue along a single ramp towards the highway, which is controlled by the traffic light S_{entry} .

III. DEEP REINFORCEMENT LEARNING APPROACH

The proposed traffic control strategy is developed with DRL based on Actor-Critic framework, which integrates value-based and policy-based methods to optimize vehicle merging. Decision making relies on three essential components: environment states, actions and rewards.

A. State Space

Let us consider a typical environment consisting of vehicles traveling in three routes:

- \mathcal{R}_{in} : vehicles entering from a motorway and attempting to merge into a second motorway;
- \mathcal{R}_{turn} : vehicles performing a turning maneuver to enter the motorway;
- \mathcal{R}_{main} : Vehicles continuing straight on the motorway without changing lanes.

At time t , the state s_t of the environment (the traffic system) is defined as:

$$s_t = \left\{ n_{\mathcal{R}_{in}}, n_{\mathcal{R}_{turn}}, n_{\mathcal{R}_{main}}, v_{\mathcal{R}_{in}}, v_{\mathcal{R}_{turn}}, v_{\mathcal{R}_{main}} \right\}$$

where

- $n_{\mathcal{R}_{in}}, n_{\mathcal{R}_{turn}}, n_{\mathcal{R}_{main}}$ denote the vehicle counts in each route ($\mathcal{R}_{in}, \mathcal{R}_{turn}, \mathcal{R}_{main}$),
- $v_{\mathcal{R}_{in}}, v_{\mathcal{R}_{turn}}, v_{\mathcal{R}_{main}}$ indicate the average vehicle speeds on the respective routes.

B. Action Space

The action space is defined as a binary vector of two elements representing the state of the two traffic lights managing vehicle entry. In particular, a first traffic light rules the inputs in the merging route and a second one rules the inputs in the motorway:

$$S_t = \begin{bmatrix} S_{merge} \\ S_{entry} \end{bmatrix}$$

where:

- $S_{merge} \in \{0, 1\}$ controls the merging traffic light, with:

$$S_{merge} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if the signal is in phase } \mathcal{GR} \\ 1, & \text{if the signal is in phase } \mathcal{RG} \end{cases}$$

- $S_{entry} \in \{0, 1\}$ controls the entry traffic light, with:

$$S_{entry} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if the signal is in phase } \mathcal{R} \\ 1, & \text{if the signal is in phase } \mathcal{G} \end{cases}$$

Thus, the action space set is:

$$\mathcal{S} = \{[0, 0]^T, [0, 1]^T, [1, 0]^T, [1, 1]^T\}$$

where each action vector S_t defines the state of both traffic lights at time t .

C. Reward Function

The reward function is designed to guarantee traffic efficiency and safety, incorporating weighted penalties for collisions, sudden decelerations, and waiting times. The reward function is defined as follows:

$$R(s, a, t) = -w_c n_c(s, a, t) - w_d d(s, a, t) - w_t t(s, a, t) \quad (1)$$

with

- $n_c(s, a, t)$: Number of collisions at time t .
- $d(s, a, t)$: Cumulative sudden deceleration.
- $t(s, a, t)$: Average waiting time.
- w_c : Weight associated with the severity of collisions.
- w_d : Weight penalizing sudden decelerations, capturing traffic instability.
- w_t : Weight penalizing waiting times, influencing traffic efficiency.

In addition, the cumulative sudden deceleration $d(s, a, t)$ is computed by summing the excessive deceleration events across all vehicles in the system. For each vehicle v , the deceleration is given by:

$$a_v(t) = \frac{v_v(t-1) - v_v(t)}{\Delta t} \quad (2)$$

where $v_v(t)$ is the velocity of vehicle v at time t . If the deceleration exceeds a predefined threshold a_{thr} , it contributes to the total penalty:

$$d(s, a, t) = \sum_{v \in V} \max(0, |a_v(t)| - |a_{\text{thr}}|). \quad (3)$$

This formulation ensures that only significant braking events influence the reward function, penalizing unstable traffic conditions and promoting smoother traffic flow.

Traditional Q-learning relies on a tabular Q-function representation, where each state-action pair is stored explicitly. However, as the state space grows, the number of entries scales exponentially, making this approach infeasible for traffic control scenarios with multiple variables. To face this problem, it is possible to use function approximation techniques such as Deep Q-Learning (DQN). However, DQN remains unsuitable for the particular characteristics of the considered problem: the continuous action space, the dynamics of the traffic conditions, inefficient policy optimization. To overcome these issues, the Actor-Critic framework combines policy optimization with value estimation. The actor network maps states to actions, supporting continuous control, while the critic network stabilizes learning by estimating value functions. This synergy enhances adaptability and efficiency in dynamic traffic management.

D. Actor-Critic Framework

The DRL model utilizes two neural networks:

- **Actor network**: maps states to actions using a probabilistic policy $\pi(a|s)$. It outputs the probability of taking each possible action in a given state;

- **Critic network**: estimates the value of a state or the advantage of an action using a value function $V(s)$ or $Q(s, a)$.

The *Actor* and *Critic* work synergistically during the learning process. The Actor selects an action based on the current policy, while the Critic evaluates the chosen action by computing an estimate of the advantage or the error. The Critic uses this error to update its parameters and provides feedback to the Actor, which consequently updates its policy to favor actions that lead to higher rewards [9].

The update of the Critic parameters is based on the *Advantage Function* and the *TD-error* (Temporal Difference error). The TD-error measures how much the received reward deviates from the expected reward.

The advantage function $A(s, a)$ of a given action a in state s is defined as the difference between the action-value function and the state-value function:

$$A(s, a) = Q(s, a) - V(s) \quad (4)$$

where:

- $Q(s, a)$ is the action-value function, representing the expected return of taking action a in state s and then following the current policy;
- $V(s)$ is the state-value function, representing the expected return of state s under the current policy.

The advantage function helps determine how much better an action is compared to the average value of the current state. Additionally, the advantage function is closely related to the TD-error used in Actor-Critic algorithms to update the Critic and, consequently, improve the Actor's policy:

$$\delta = r + \gamma V(s') - V(s), \quad (5)$$

where r is the reward, γ is the discount factor, s is the current state, and s' is the next state.

Network Architecture: Both Actor and Critic are implemented as fully-connected neural networks with the following architecture:

- **Input layer**: dimension equal to the number of state features;
- **Hidden layers**: three dense layers with 128, 64, and 32 units respectively, each using the ReLU activation function;
- **Actor output layer**: one dense layer with as many units as possible actions, activated with `softmax` to produce a probability distribution over actions;
- **Critic output layer**: a single neuron with `linear` activation, producing a scalar estimate of the state value.

The Actor network is trained using the `categorical_crossentropy` loss function, suitable for probabilistic output, and optimized with the Adam optimizer ($\alpha = 10^{-3}$). The Critic is trained via `mean_squared_error` to minimize the discrepancy between the predicted and target state values, using the same optimizer configuration.

IV. CASE STUDY

To evaluate the proposed DRL-based traffic control approach, a case study was conducted at the intersection of the A1 Highway and the A14 Motorway near Casalecchio di Reno, a major and strategically important traffic node in central-northern Italy. This location was selected due to its high traffic volumes, complex ramp geometry, and frequent merging conflicts, making it an ideal testbed for assessing the system’s adaptability and effectiveness under real-world highway conditions.

A. Simulation Environment

The simulation was implemented using SUMO tool. The network topology was extracted from OpenStreetMap (OSM) and converted into a SUMO-compatible format using `netconvert`. The merging scenario was modeled to reflect real-world conditions, including:

- High variability in vehicle speeds and densities, with traffic including both fast-moving cars and slower vehicles, resulting in dynamic interactions;
- Traffic lights at critical points to manage merging conflicts. Two traffic lights $\mathcal{S}_{\text{merge}}$, $\mathcal{S}_{\text{entry}}$ were introduced, alternating between green and red states to regulate traffic flow.

The three primary routes modeled in the simulation include:

- \mathcal{R}_{in} : Vehicles entering from the A14 motorway and attempting to merge into the A1 via the Casalecchio node. This section is characterized by high entry volumes and short acceleration zones, leading to frequent merging conflicts.
- $\mathcal{R}_{\text{turn}}$: Vehicles coming from the A1 and performing a turning maneuver to enter the Bologna ring road (Tangenziale). This requires traversing multiple lanes and ramp segments, increasing the likelihood of congestion and unsafe maneuvers.
- $\mathcal{R}_{\text{main}}$: Vehicles continuing straight on the A1 without changing lanes. This stream serves as the primary flow and acts as a baseline for evaluating disturbances caused by merging and turning vehicles.

B. Implementation Details and Performance Indices

The scenario presented in Fig. 2 was implemented with the following key steps:

- 1) Map extraction: The network layout of the area was exported from OSM and saved in the `.osm` format.
- 2) Network conversion: The `netconvert` tool was used to transform the OSM file into a SUMO-compatible `.net.xml` file, capturing road geometries, lanes, and traffic rules.
- 3) Route definition: Using `netedit`, three main routes \mathcal{R}_{in} , $\mathcal{R}_{\text{turn}}$, and $\mathcal{R}_{\text{main}}$ were defined to simulate different traffic patterns, focusing on critical merging and conflict points.
- 4) Traffic light configuration: Two traffic lights were introduced to regulate vehicle flows at key junctions,

alternating states between green \mathcal{G} and \mathcal{R} based on predefined sequences.

Fig. 2. Geometric layout of the intersection between the A1 Highway and the A14 Motorway near Casalecchio di Reno, Bologna. The figure illustrates the merging zones, directional ramps, and traffic flow interactions, which serve as an alternative test environment for evaluating the proposed DRL-based traffic control strategy.

The effectiveness of the DRL-based control strategy was evaluated using the performance indices summarized in Table I.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE INDICES

Metric	Description
Collision frequency	Number of collisions recorded during the simulation, focusing on minimizing incidents in high-conflict zones.
Sudden braking events	Total deceleration events exceeding 4.5 m/s^2 , indicating potential risks and traffic inefficiencies.
Average waiting time	Average delay experienced by vehicles at the merging zone, calculated for all three routes.

C. Training Phase of the Traffic Light

The agent (the traffic light) was trained over 600 episodes, each consisting of 150 steps. These parameters were chosen to ensure adequate exploration of the environment and allow the agent to learn optimal decision-making strategies in a simulated traffic scenario. The reward function was carefully designed with the following weights to prioritize different objectives:

- Collisions: $w_c = 100$ was assigned to collisions to reflect their critical severity;
- Waiting times: $w_t = 10$ for the highway ramp, 5 for route $\mathcal{R}_{\text{turn}}$, and 1 for route $\mathcal{R}_{\text{main}}$;
- Sudden braking events: $w_d = 1$ was assigned to penalize abrupt decelerations.

During the initial training phases, a temporary deterioration in performance was observed, as the agent performed suboptimal exploratory actions to gather information about the environment. However, as training progressed, the agent transitioned into the exploitation phase, leading to notable improvements in key metrics. This trend is reflected in the reward

progression shown in Fig. 3: an increase in reward values indicates improved decision-making and better adaptation to traffic conditions over time.

Fig. 3. Evolution of the cumulative reward during the training phase. The plot illustrates the learning progress of the DRL agent.

D. Evaluation Phase

After completing the training, the solution was tested in new simulations to evaluate the robustness of the learned policies. During this phase, the optimized weights of the Actor and Critic networks were loaded, and the exploration mechanism was disabled. This deterministic approach ensured that the agent applied the acquired policies directly.

The key metrics analyzed during the testing phase included the following results. The average waiting time on the highway ramp and routes was significantly reduced compared to baseline scenarios:

- **Scenario 1:** Traffic regulated using SUMO's default management system, where traffic lights operate with static cycles of 30 seconds without optimization.
- **Scenario 2:** DRL-based traffic control with dynamic phase adjustments to optimize vehicle flow and minimize congestion.

The number of vehicles present on different routes was monitored to assess traffic density. Finally, the total amount of deceleration experienced by vehicles decreased.

E. Discussion of Results and Comparative Analysis

The proposed DRL framework was tested and validated through a set of simulations using the SUMO platform. The experiments were designed to evaluate the agent's ability to optimize traffic flow and improve safety metrics in the highway merging scenario. A comparative analysis was conducted on a single episode consisting of 400 steps to highlight the benefits of the intelligent traffic light control introduced by the DRL framework. The two scenarios discussed in the testing phase were evaluated.

The results of this comparison indicated that the intelligent traffic lights managed by the DRL agent significantly improved overall network efficiency. Moreover, the proposed control strategy reduced the Average Waiting Times, Number of cars and Deceleration as it shown in Fig. 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, respectively. In particular, Fig. 4, 5, and 6 perform the

comparison of average waiting times between the DRL-based control strategy and the baseline traffic management approach for \mathcal{R}_{in} , \mathcal{R}_{turn} and \mathcal{R}_{main} , respectively. The results indicate a significant reduction in delays at merging points, highlighting the efficiency of adaptive traffic light control.

In addition, Fig. 7, 8 compare the vehicle counts on \mathcal{R}_{in} and \mathcal{R}_{main} , respectively, between the proposed DRL framework and the baseline strategy. The analysis reveals an improved distribution of traffic, leading to reduced congestion in critical merging areas. Finally, Fig. 9 reports the cumulative deceleration values between the DRL-based traffic management system and the baseline approach: the reduction in sudden braking events suggests improved traffic flow and enhanced safety.

Fig. 4. Comparison of average waiting times between the DRL-based control strategy and the baseline traffic management approach for \mathcal{R}_{in} .

Fig. 5. Comparison of average waiting times between the DRL-based control strategy and the baseline traffic management approach for \mathcal{R}_{turn} .

Fig. 6. Comparison of average waiting times between the DRL-based control strategy and the baseline traffic management approach for \mathcal{R}_{main} .

Fig. 7. Comparison of vehicle count on \mathcal{R}_{in} between the proposed DRL framework and the baseline strategy.

Fig. 8. Comparison of vehicle count on \mathcal{R}_{main} between the proposed DRL framework and the baseline strategy.

Fig. 9. Comparison of cumulative deceleration values between the DRL-based traffic management system and the baseline approach.

V. CONCLUSION

This study introduces a Deep Reinforcement Learning framework to optimize vehicle merging at highway ramps and intersections, using an actor-critic approach to improve traffic safety and efficiency. The proposed model effectively reduces congestion, sudden braking, and collision risks by enabling adaptive decision-making through a customized reward function.

The framework was validated using a case study at the intersection of the A1 Highway and the A14 Motorway near Casalecchio di Reno, a major and complex traffic node in

central-northern Italy. This location was selected due to its high traffic volumes, intricate ramp geometry, and frequent merging conflicts, making it a representative environment for evaluating the system's adaptability and effectiveness.

Future research will focus on scaling the approach to larger networks, integrating real-time Internet of Things, Vehicle-to-Infrastructure, and Vehicle-to-Vehicle communication, and exploring multi-agent reinforcement learning to enhance coordination and adaptability in traffic management.

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